

MODIFICATION OF COLLIN'S METHOD FOR DETERMINING CARBONATE IN SOILS

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A rapid method for the estimation of carbonate in soils has been described. Use is made of a solution of trichloroacetic acid (150 g. acid in 10 g. water) to liberate the carbon dioxide. The volume of carbon dioxide evolved from pure calcium carbonate is measured. An amount of soil equal to 100 divided by the volume of carbon dioxide evolved from 0.100 g. calcium carbonate is taken for liberating carbon dioxide. The volume of carbon dioxide then evolved divided by 10 gives directly the percentage of calcium carbonate in the soil. The apparatus used is also described and is simple to set up.

Several methods are available for determining the amount of carbonate in soils. Some of the gravimetric and volumetric methods are very accurate and

Fig. 1

carbonate content of the soil can be determined to the second or even third decimal place. In routine examination of soils such accuracy is not only unessential but even the time and labour devoted to it are not commensurate with the significance of the determination. In soil laboratories Collin's Calcimeter method has found wide application. It measures the amount of carbon dioxide evolved from a given weight of the sample under specified conditions and from the amount of carbon dioxide evolved the percentage of calcium carbonate in soils is calculated.

It has to be recognised that in such a determination a small quantity of a gas other than that from calcium carbonate gives higher readings as is evident from the work of Shorey and Martin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4907) and others, and for the highest accuracy the method described by Schollenberger (*Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 307; 1945, 59, 57) is an ideal one. In the Collins' original method dilute HCl is used for liberating carbon dioxide. It has been shown by Erickson, Li and Gieseeking (*Soil Sci.*, 1947, 63 451) that a solution of trichloroacetic acid is a better reagent.

In the present method trichloroacetic acid has been used for liberating carbon dioxide.

Another modification adopted is to do away with the measurement of temperature and pressure and reduction of volume at N. T. P. In this way it is possible to carry out a number of estimations rapidly and with sufficient accuracy.

Apparatus.—Laboratories having Collin's calcimeter can use that apparatus for such determinations. For laboratories that do not have this apparatus the set up is quite simple, and is shown in Fig. 1.

A gas burette and an ordinary burette are connected by a piece of pressure tubing. The other end of the gas burette is connected by a piece of pressure tubing to a 150 c.c. wide mouthed ether extraction flask. The flask is fitted with a two-hole stopper. In one of the holes is fitted a glass stop-cock, while a piece of glass tubing is inserted in the other hole and connected to the burette. One small test tube of 2-2½" length having a capacity of 8 c.c. is used to fill acid.

Reagents.—Pure calcium carbonate and a solution prepared from 150 g. of trichloroacetic acid and 10 g. of water are used.

Procedure.—Pure calcium carbonate (0.10 g.) is weighed and introduced into the flask. The trichloroacetic acid solution (5 c.c.) is added to the test tube and the test tube wiped from outside. It is carefully inserted into the flask which is closed and hung by a hook on the apparatus. It is connected to the gas burette by pressure tubing. The heights of water columns in the two burettes are adjusted to the same level and the glass tap is closed. The acid is then carefully permitted to flow into the flask by tilting it and shaking it well. After the evolution of carbon dioxide ceases, the levels in the burettes are again adjusted and the volume of carbon dioxide is read off. *Towards the end it is advisable to check up the leakage by lowering the open burette and keeping it there for five minutes. This estimation gives the amount of soil to be taken for direct determination of the percentage of carbonate.

If the volume of the gas evolved is V c.c. the quantity of soil to be taken for direct determination is $100/V$ g.

Weigh $100/V$ g. of the soil to be tested and repeat the above procedure. The volume of carbon dioxide evolved divided by 10 gives directly the percentage of calcium carbonate in the soil.

Suppose a g. calcium carbonate is present in $100/V$ g. of soil and V_1 c.c. of carbon dioxide is evolved from it at temperature T_1° (abs.) and pressure P_1 mm. of mercury. The volume of carbon dioxide at N.T.P.

$$= \frac{V_1 \times P_1 \times 273}{760 \times T_1}$$

But the volume of carbon dioxide given by 0.100 g. of calcium carbonate is V c.c. at temperature T_1 and pressure P_1 and the volume at N.T.P.

$$= \frac{V \times P_1 \times 273}{760 \times T_1}$$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{a}{0.1} = \frac{\frac{V_1 \times P_1 \times 273}{760 \times T_1}}{\frac{V \times P_1 \times 273}{760 \times T_1}} = \frac{V_1}{V}$$

Therefore $a = \frac{V_1}{10V}$ g. calcium carbonate in $\frac{100}{W}$ g. of soil.

$$\therefore \text{Percentage of calcium carbonate in the soil} = \frac{V_1}{10V} \times \frac{100}{1} \times \frac{V}{100} = \frac{V_1}{10}$$

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